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Examination of Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) States of Students Who Study at the School of Physical Education and Sports in Terms of Some Variables

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the frequency rate of FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) in both male and female students under some variables. Social media platforms which became an inseparable part of daily life have caused individuals to spend more time in the virtual world. From Sports Sciences, a total of 465 students (274 males and 191 females) who study in different departments and who are in different grades have participated in the present study which is pretty limited available in Turkish in the literature. In the research, "Fear of Missing Out in Social Settings Scale" the Turkish version that is adapted by (Gökler et al., 2016) of the scale "Motivational, emotional, and behavioral correlates of fear of missing out" which is developed by (Przybylski, 2013) was used as a data collection tool. In the present study, statistical analysis of data has been performed through SPSS 26 program, t-tests, and One Way ANOVA tests. According to T-test results of FOMO averages based on sex, no significant difference has been found. It has been established that students who are not engaged in any sports activity ($X=4.05$) have a higher rate of FOMO on social media as compared to those who play sports ($X=2.95$), it has been established that students who check their phones right after they wake up ($X=3.70$) and students who spend time with their phones before sleeping ($X=3.75$) have higher FOMO averages as compared to those who don't check ($X=3.40$) or spend time with their phones ($X=3.42$). A significant difference has been detected ($p>0.05$). According to One Way ANOVA Post-toc tests which were based on daily social media usage durations and departments of the students. No significant difference has been established FOMO levels of students based on the grade they are in and the number of social media they own.

Keywords: Education, Physical Education, Student, FOMO, Social Media, Social Media Addiction, Computer

1. Introduction

When the last century is regarded, revolutionary developments have occurred through gradually undergoing a number of changes in the historical process. One of these developments is the internet, which has become a part

of our lives.

With the invention of the World Wide Web (www) by Tim Berners-Lee (Berners-Lee et al., 2001) at the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) in 1990 (Castells, 2005) access to internet was provided to public majorly, along with the usage of the World Wide Web in 1991.

The concept of traditional media has undergone a radical change. During this period which is called Web 1.0, people have been offered some limited opportunities in which there are few servers to obtain information, information could be read unilaterally, and no one could interact with one another.(KAPAN & ÜNCEL). The development of Web 2.0 technology can be called the birth of the social media which enable communication and sharing.(Mavnacıoğlu, 2017). With this developing technology, social media stand out as one of the most effective platforms in terms of interpersonal communication with its features such as constant upgradability, the possibility for multiple usage, more widespread possibilities for virtual sharing, etc. The concept of social media has started to take place in our lives as an alternative to classical media since the day it appeared. Gradually, the usage of social media has become one of the main purposes of internet usage.

Within the scope of all these developments, the concept of FOMO (Fear Of Missing Out), which is originated from the individuals' fear of social exclusion(Blackwell et al., 2017; Przybylski et al., 2013).has been formulated, and this concept has also entered the Oxford dictionary and has effectively begun to appear in dictionaries. (Ulaşırın, 2017). The concept of FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) is defined in different ways in the literature. It is defined as “concern that others may have a good experience in his absence (Przybylski et al., 2013), in one of those definitions and in the Oxford dictionary, it is “Anxiety that an exciting or interesting event may currently be happening elsewhere”. It results in people constantly communicating via social media in order not to miss something (Oberst et al., 2017; Wiesner, 2017). Social media seems to be an important tool in eliminating FOMO, which arises from the need of individuals to belong to a group.(Wiesner, 2017).

It is seen that platforms which have been used most frequently and have had millions of users since the internet addiction (Aktan, 2018) such as WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Snapchat, Twitter, Swarm, Pinterest, Tumblr, LinkedIn, Google+, second life, Pinterest, flicker have a huge determinative impact on the youth.(Li et al., 2007). Along with the actively widespread usage of social media by the users from general public and university youth, presidents, universities, government agencies, corporations and firms(Ergenç, 2013), felt the need to be in this platform actively.

Along with the Internet, drastic changes have occurred in both fields such as individual, commercial, tourism activities (Çetinkaya & Şahbaz, 2019), social, military intelligence (Savaş & Topaloğlu, 2016; Tiryaki et al., 2020) and marketing strategies and social life.(İnce & KOÇAK, 2017). The decisiveness of social media plays an active role in the widespread usage of the Internet among young people especially, in Turkey and the whole world. Accordingly, it has been seen that many academicians also do their scientific research on students the most (Ayhan & Çavuş, 2014).

2. Method

2.1 The Aim of The Study

The aim of this study is to examine the fear of missing out on social media in which the youth and especially students who study in sports sciences show a great deal of interest, and FOMO prevalence in the rates of using social networks for both male and female students in terms of some variables.

2.2 Data Collection Tool

In the study, “Motivational, emotional, and behavioral correlates of fear of missing out” (Przybylski et al., 2013) and “Scale of FOMO On Social Media Platforms” which was adapted to Turkish by (Gökler et al., 2016). (AYDIN, 2016). There is no negative (reverse) item in the scale that consists of a single dimension and a total of 10 items. Items on the 5-point Likert-type scale are scored as 1 Not at all True, Partly Not True 2, Moderately True 3, Quite

True 4, and Extremely True 5. The more the total score which is taken from the scale increase the more the possibility of individuals having FOMO on social media platforms also increase.

2.3 Analysis of the Data

The data which were obtained through the Google form were transferred to the IBM SPSS 26 program and reliability, frequency, percentiles, arithmetic averages, and standard deviations of the data have been calculated. For the analysis of independent variables, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to determine the supposition of normal distribution of the data. (Büyüköztürk et al., 2011; Büyüköztürk, 2011). As a result of the conclusions that were obtained, kurtosis and skewness values were also examined. JAPA (Büyüköztürk et al., 2011); (George & Mallery, 2010). As a result of the analysis, these values were found to be between -1.5 and +1.5. For this reason, it was determined that it fulfilled the assumption of normality.(Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Parametric tests were used for the analysis and interpretation of the data. Accordingly, the t-test analysis was performed to determine whether there was a significant difference the FOMO on social media based on the parameters such as Sex, Active Sporting Activity, Checking The Smartphone Right After Waking Up, Spending Time With The Smartphone Before Sleeping and The Sports Group That Is Engaged With.

One-Way Anova test analyzes were examined based on The Departments of The Participants, Durations of Daily Social Media Usage, and The Number of Social Media Accounts Of Participants. After the examination, LSD tests among PostHoc tests were used in cases where the variances were homogeneous, and the Games-Howell test among PostHoc tests were used in cases where the variances did not fullfil homogeneity, in order to determine the source of the difference in cases where the relation between the variables was significant.

3. Findings

At this chapter, statical analysis conclusions of the data which are obtained from FOMO on social media platforms scale have been interpreted after being tabulated.

3.1. Definitive Characteristics

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distributions on the definitive characteristics of the research group

Variables	<i>f</i>	%	
Sex	Male	274	58.9
	Female	191	41.1
Departments	Physical Education	113	24.3
	Sports Management	124	26.7
	Coaching Education	116	24.9
	Recreation	112	24.1
Grades	1 st Grade	135	29
	2 nd Grade	129	27.7
	3 rd Grade	114	24.5
	4 th Grade	87	18.7
Engagement In a Sportive Activity Actively	Yes	187	40.2
	No	278	59.8
Duration of Daily Usage of Social Media	Less Than 1 Hour	130	28
	Between 1-3 Hours	124	26.7
	4-6 Hours	121	26

	7 Hours and Above	90	19.4
The Number of Accounts That Is Owned on Social Media	1	166	35.7
	2	147	31.6
	3 and More	152	32.7
The state of Checking The Smartphone Right After Waking Up	Yes	324	64.7
	No	141	35.3
The State of Spending Time with the Smartphone Before Sleeping	Yes	259	45.8
	No	206	54.2
Duration of Social Media Account Ownership	1-2 Years	164	35.3
	3-4 Years	149	32
	More Than 5 Years	152	32.7
Sports Group Branch Which Is Engaged	Individual Sports	225	48.4
	Team Sports	240	51.6

When Table 1, which includes data on descriptive demographic characteristics, is examined, 274 of the students who participate in the research are male and 191 of them are female. When the department variables are examined, 113 of the students who participate in the research study in Physical Education and Sports Education, 124 in Sports Management, 116 in Coaching Education, 112 in Recreation Department, and when the grade variable of the participants is examined, 135 are in 1st grade, 129 of them are in 2nd grade. It is seen that 114 of them are in the 3rd grade and 87 of them are in the 4th grade. It is seen that whereas 59.8% of the participants do active sports, 40.2% do not participate in sports activities, 48.4% are interested in individual sports, 51.6% are interested in team sports.

When the social media variables are regarded, 64.7% of the participants consists of people who check their phones right after waking up, 45% of those consist of people who check their phones before sleeping, and 35.7% of them own at least one, 31.6% of them own two, 32.7% of them own three or more social media accounts. Regarding the variable of duration of social media usage, it is seen that 28% of them use social media less than 1 hour a day, 26.7% use 1-2 hours, 26% use social media between 4-6 hours, 19.4% use social media for 7 hours or more. When the length of social media account usage is examined, 35.3% stated that they have been on social media for 1-2 years, %32 for 3-4 years, and % 32.7 for more than 5 years.

Table 2 shows the results of the t-test analysis, which was conducted to determine the statistical differences between FOMO on social media levels and demographic characteristics of the participants who study at the School of Physical Education and Sports.

Table 2: T-test results of the scores of fomo on social media platforms scale based on the demographic variables

Variables	Groups	N	X	ss	T-test		
					t	sd	p
Fear of Missing Out on Social Media	Male	274	3.57	.98	-971	424	.332
	Female	191	3.66	.92			
Engagement In A Sportive Activity Actively	Yes	187	2.95	.84	-14.633	463	.000*
	No	278	4.05	.75			

The state of Checking The Smartphone Right After Waking Up	Yes	324	3.70	.96	3.182	463	.002*
	No	141	3.40	.91			
The State of Spending Time with the Smartphone Before Sleeping	Yes	259	3.75	.93	3.748	463	.000*
	No	206	3.42	.96			
Engagement In Sports Group	Individual	225	3.57	.97	-.807	463	.420
	Team	240	3.64	.94			

* significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level

When the levels of FOMO on social media, which are given in Table 2, have been analyzed by sex, there is no significant difference between male and female participants. ($t[971] = -.332$; $p > 0.05$). It is seen that FOMO levels of male students are ($X = 3.57$) and the ones of female students are ($X = 3.66$). It is seen that there is a significant difference between the participants who engage in active sports activities and those who do not engage in any sports activities. ($t[-14,633] = -.000$; $p < 0.05$). The FOMO on social media levels ($X = 4.05$) of those who do not participate in sportive activities are seen to be more than the FOMO levels of the participants who engage in sportive activities. ($X = 2.95$). It is seen that there is a significant difference between those who check their smartphones right after they wake up in the morning and those who do not check their phones when they wake up. ($t[3,182] = -.002$; $p < 0.05$). FOMO levels of the participants who checked their phones right after they wake up were found to be ($X = 3.70$) and the FOMO levels of the participants who do not check their phones when they wake up are ($X = 3.40$). Considering the other variables, a significant difference was found between FOMO levels of those who spend time with their smart phones right before sleeping, and those who do not spend time with their phones before sleeping ($t[3,748] = -.0000$; $p < 0.05$) asleep.

It is seen that those who spend time with their smartphones before sleeping are ($X = 3.75$), and those who do not spend time with their phone before sleeping are ($X = 3.42$). Based on the Interested Sports Group Branch. There is no significant difference between the FOMO levels of individual and team sports. ($t[-.807] = .420$; $p > 0.05$).

The results of the one-way variance analysis (ANOVA) which is conducted to determine whether there is a relationship between the FOMO on social media based on the departments are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Anova results of scores of fomo on social media platforms out scale based on the departments of participants

Departments	N	X	Ss	Variance Source	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significance
Physical Education -1	113	3,698	1,040	Between Groups	19,726	3	6,575	7,429	.000*	1-4; 2-4; 3-4
Sport Management -2	124	3,793	.857	Within Groups	408,030	461	.885			
Coaching Education -3	116	3,681	.853	Total	427,755	464				
Recreation -4	112	3,255	1.008							
Total	465	3,612	.960							

* significant difference at $p < 0.05$ level

When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference among the rates of FOMO on social media ($F=7.29$; $p<.0.05$).

According to the results of the Games-Howell test, which was conducted to indicate that the FOMO on Social Media of the Participants differs based on their departments; it is observed that students who study in departments such as the physical education, ($X=3,698$), sports management ($X=3,793$) and coaching departments ($X=3,681$) have a higher rate of FOMO as compared to the students who study in recreation department. ($X=3,225$).

The results of the one-way variance (ANOVA) analysis which was conducted to determine whether there is a relationship between the FOMO on social media based on Duration of Daily Social Media Usage are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Anova results of scores of fomo on social media platforms scale based on durations of daily social media usage

Daily Social Media Variance Duration	N	X	Ss	Variance Source	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significance
Less Than 1 Hour (1)	130	3,613	.984	Between Groups	7.224	3	2.408			
Between 1-3 Hours (2)	124	3,478	.933	Within Groups	420,531	461	.912			
Between 4-6 Hours (3)	121	3,577	986	Total	427,755	464		2,640	.049	4-2, 4-3;
7 Hours and Above (4)	90	3,84	.897							
Total	465	3,612	.960							

* significant difference at $p<.0.05$ level

When Table 4 is examined, it is observed that there is a significant difference in FOMO on social media rates based on the duration of daily social media usage of the participants ($F=2.640$; $p<.0.05$).

According to the results of the LSD test, which was conducted to determine that the rates of FOMO on Social media of the participants differs based on their social media usage durations, individuals who spend 7 hours or more on social media ($X=3.84$), have a higher rate of FOMO on social media as compared to those who spend 1-3 hours ($X=3.85$) and 4- Between 6 Hours ($X=3.57$) There is no significant difference between individuals who spend less than 1 hour ($X=3.61$) and 1-3 hours ($X=3.47$).

Table 5 shows the results of the one-way variance (ANOVA) analysis which was conducted to determine whether there is a relationship between rates of FOMO on social media based on the Number of Accounts that participants Own on Social Media.

Table 5: Anova results of scores of fomo on social media platforms scale based on the number of social media accounts that the participants own

Account Number	N	X	Ss	Variance Source	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significance
1 (1)	166	3,580	1.005	Between Groups	.288	2	.144	.156	.806	-

2 (2)	147	3,623	.981	Within Groups	427,4 67	46 2	.925
3 + (3)	152	3,637	.891	Total	427,7 55	46 4	
Total	465	3,612	.960				

When Table 5 is examined, no significant difference has been seen based on the number of social media accounts of students ($F=.156$; $p<.0,05$).

Table 6: The anova results of the fomo on social media platforms scale based on the grades that participants are in

Grades	N	X	Ss	Variance Source	KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significance
1 st Grade (1)	135	3,699	.945	Between Groups	5,823	3	1,941			
2 nd Grade (2)	129	3,444	1.04	Within Groups	421,932	461	.915			
3 rd Grade (3)	114	3,613	.960	Total	427,755	464		2,121	.097*	-
4 th Grade (4)	87	3,727	.894							
Totals	465	3,612	.960							

* significant difference is at $p<0.05$ level

When Table 6 is examined, no significant difference has been found based on the grades they are in, on their FOMO.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Increase in new technologies which include private computers, PCs and smartphones and virtual communication not only have facilitated the life but also have paved the way for various changes in daily habits and behaviors of individuals.

In the present study, there is no significant difference in FOMO averages based on sex. In a similar study that was conducted by (Jood, 2017), and (KIRIK et al., 2015) it has been reported that there is no significant difference in sex variables and the scale, either. It is established that students who have the habit of checking their smartphones right after waking up and students who spend time with their smartphones right before sleeping have a higher rate of FOMO.

The reason of the tendency for smartphones in the youth might be the impact of behaviors such as following the updates on social media, viewing the posts, status updates.

In the present study that was conducted thanks to the voluntary participation of 465 university students who study in the faculty of sports sciences, It has been observed that there are significant differences in terms of some variables in FOMO rates. It has been established that there are statically significant differences in FOMO averages based on the durations of social media usage on a daily basis and departments of participants. Based on that, it can be stated that there is a positive relation between FOMO levels of participants and the durations which are spent in social media.

No significant difference has been established between FOMO averages of the grades that participants are in and the number of social media accounts they own. No significant difference has been established between FOMO

averages and the number of social media accounts they own. It has been established that the students who study in recreation department have a lower average of FOMO. However it is observed that in the literature, there are studies which oppose to the conclusions that were found in this study, as well.(AKILLI & GEZGİN, 2016; Gökler et al., 2016).

Along with these information and communication technologies, the arising of some issues have been inevitable. These issues caused parents and teachers to be concerned about possible negative outcomes and practices of excessive or wrong use by children and teens.(Oberst et al., 2017).

The issues which arise from students' spending long durations on social media platforms and their desire to be liked should be solved with methods that enable systematic control, instead of methods that contribute to deprivation. Therefore, purposes of the internet usage in the favor of students will be supported.

It has been observed that individuals who have high rates of FOMO are also people who have many desires to be liked (Yıldırım,2016). It's thought that in order for the duration that is spent in social media platforms to be decreased, students can be occupied with various social, artistic and sportive activities and therefore FOMO will decrease accordingly. Such setups can be planned in a way that might raise the level of awareness of the students. The fact that the students who study in recreation department have lowest level of FOMO reinforces the importance of this recommendation.

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